

Supporting large scale XAS processing, analysis and FAIR publishing with scientific workflows.

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Large-scale facilities generate valuable, high-quality XAS data. However, as experiments become more complex and datasets grow, the time required for data processing and analysis increases, making manual approaches impractical. The additional expectation to publish FAIR supporting data further complicates sharing data and impacts researchers time. There are several key challenges including limited support for reproducibility and reuse beyond the original study, lack of explicit provenance links between published results and underlying data, and incomplete or improperly curated published data.

Using Galaxy and a set of XAS Galaxy Tools, employing on X-Ray Larch, we demonstrate how workflow-based processing and structured packaging can improve the creation of FAIR XAS datasets. We evaluated this approach by designing an experiment involving diverse supporting data extracted from selected publications. Our analysis revealed several FAIRness and completeness issues that hinder reproducibility, even when authors made substantial efforts to document and share their datasets.

In contrast, the proposed approach using Galaxy packages all relevant data and metadata in RO-Crate format, streamlining publication and enhancing transparency. Galaxy RO-Crates, provided as supporting materials, facilitate data sharing, reproducibility, and provenance tracking, contributing to the advancement of FAIR research practices in catalysis.

The XAS Galaxy tools and workflows are available for testing and further use. In this talk we will also present how we are updating the XAS Galaxy tools to process data conforming to IXAS-IUCr recommended standards, NeXus XAS and XDI as part of the OSCARS project.

Keywords: XAFS Processing, XAFS Analysis, Large Datasets, Scientific Workflows and FAIR publishing

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